
Feminism in *A Room with View* Novel: A Critical Analysis

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Abstract

Feminist play with a range of choice in the process self-presentation, registering a relation both to the body and to the social meaning of womanhood. The focus of this research is comparing and measuring the feminist issues by reading the novel "A Room with a View". The purpose of this study is describing feminist issues that happened in the novel. This type of research is qualitative descriptive, the writer uses observation documentation as the technique of gaining and measuring data with reading intensively. The sample data in this research was every scenes that the writer belief the dialogue was consisting with feminism act, read intensively in every scenes. Based on the observation, the writer find some topic and issues that happened in the novel "A Room with a View", the problem faced by the author is the language style used in the novel, so the writer decide to read intensively to knowing the true meaning of each dialogues. This research concluded that there was a lot of feminism issues that happened in the novel "A Room with a View" even though there are still obstacles with problems to understand with the language style.

Keywords: *feminism, a room with a view, novel, critical analysis*

1. Background

Literature is a reflection of the various ideas, experiences, and desires of humans in their daily lives which are expressed in the form and style of their literary works. Because literature itself also comes directly from various human lives, it can also add experience and learning about the problems experienced by humans, including morals, culture and values of human interests. According to Wellek and Warren (1956, p.15) literature is a creative activity, and art without artistic value is not art. Along with scientific works, reports, and other forms of writing, literature will be just another type of writing. It also increases human understanding or insight, enriches their souls, and makes them more civilized (Millar & Currie, 1970). This can assist them in comprehending the circumstances and attributes of others. As a result, literature has aided human development on both a personal and

intellectual level. It serves as an objective foundation for his comprehension and knowledge. It establishes a link between them and the larger philosophical, cultural, and religious environment in which they will be immersed. A novel is a genre of literary work in and of itself. It has been generally defined as a reflection of what we have experienced and witnessed in actual life. Because the novel discusses human actions and depicts what is going on around them, it has also disclosed some characteristics of human love and human form.

This novel tells part of the appeal of *A Room with a View* very much like a modern romantic comedy novel. Their tension, from a girl getting involved with one guy but the girl falling in love with another guy. Lucy Honeychurch, engaged to Cecil Vyse, is socially compatible, but very involved and influential; she was actually in love with George Emerson, a handsome young man deemed too socially appropriate. For the second part of the novel, Lucy has completely denied her feelings, so the reader will feel a sense of tension that builds chemistry, both this and her very awkward relationship with Cecil, and they are finally allowed therapeutic relief when she finally realizes the truth of the situation and her condition returns to Florence with George.

One of the views in the novel is that the novel fits into the structure of a romantic narrative: the heroine has fallen for the wrong man, and the villain, but eventually realizes her mistake and tries to give her affection to the true hero who has been faithfully waiting for her. However, while annoying as this novel is hardly evil, and George is not the real hero, Dan is in this novel to see and investigate the complexities of possible or suggested relationships between men and women.

Considering that feminist theory is a women's movement to reject all forms of oppression in politics, economy, and social life. The link between feminism theory and Lucy's marginalized status in general. Lucy fights for equality by declaring that she wants to be with the person she loves. According to Linda Gordan (2002, p.6), feminism is also an examination of women's subordination with the goal of finding solutions to change it. Feminism, for Gordan, also includes supporting efforts to improve women's influence in the home, community, and society. Gordon has also characterized feminism as a critique of male supremacy on another occasion, which has been suggested to shift its framework.

The author chose features of the main character Struggle of Women based on a variety of factors, including the fact that this aspect of EM Forster's novel *A Room with a View* has never been studied previously. The reader can grasp the significance of struggle in life because of the main character's battle in the romantic struggle. The difficulty of life in the novel, particularly the battle to accept reality that is applicable to today's life, because Lucy must realize that her love story cannot always be together, making Lucy uncomfortable.

This study has a practical application; students and readers will benefit from it. Students can use this material to gain a better understanding of a woman's struggle in the novel *A Room With A View*. In addition, by incorporating a woman's struggle in the novel *A Room With A View*, this research attempts to help readers communicate in a more harmonious manner. The struggle of a woman, as portrayed by Lucy in the novel *A Room With A View*, will be the focus of this research. The author has also looked at many forms of women's challenges, such as how the main heroine in the novel *A Room With A View* fights to find love.

2. Literature Review

Feminism and literary work are inextricably linked. Poetry, prose, and novels are examples of literary work as a human's creative effort that incorporates various sorts of life. The goal to end male supremacy in society spawned feminist beliefs and movements. Through feminism initiatives (thoughts and movements), patriarchal and state-authoritarian structures of culture, art, church, law, and the nuclear family, as well as any images, institutions, rituals, and habits that make women victims who are not valued and hidden, must be eradicated (Ruthven, 1985: 6). Feminists recognize that their movement is rooted in women's understanding, as they are routinely oppressed and exploited, and that this must change. Furthermore, the feminism movement fights for men's level of equality and prestige, as well as the right to regulate their own bodies and lives both within and outside the family. According to Harsono in Mustaqim (2008), feminism is a concept that emerges in relation to social change, development theories, women's political consciousness, and women's liberation movements, including to readdress family systems in the context of modern society. Feminism is a style of thinking about women's rights and roles in order to make them more ideal and equal, free of discrimination, marginalization, and oppression (Mustaqim, 2008).

Feminism is an endeavor to end women's oppression and exploitation, not a rebellion against men, a fight against social institutions like marriage and domestic institutions, or women's attempts to reject their natural state. Feminism's objective in this situation is to struggle for human rights, not only gender equality. Its movement aims to transform inequitable societal institutions and structures into ones that benefit men and women equally (Fakih, 2013).

Wilany (2017) stated that women are discriminated against in society based on rules and culture. In her work, she discusses feminism and women's struggles for equal rights. Firdaus battled for her rights as a woman by claiming to be passive in the face of all the accusations leveled against her.

The study conducted by Helmanita, Emzir, and Rafli (2018) on the title Critical Discourse Analysis on Ideology of Feminism in Nawal Al-Mudzakkirat Sa'adawi's *Thobibah* aims to conduct a critical discourse analysis on the ideology of feminism in the novel *Mudzakkirat Thobibah* by Nawal Al-Sa. The conclusions include a sound metaphor of patriarchy since women are uneducated and face educational oppression, an inequality of antonyms and synonyms, and in the text's structure, the hegemony of power takes the form of character conversation. From the result, the researcher recommends a new educational curriculum design to advocate for feminist education in linguistic awareness.

3. Method

The writers adopted qualitative descriptive method and used documentation to measuring and gaining the data. The sample of this research got from every dialogues that the writer belief there was feminism issues in those dialogues, with read intensively beside of reading the novel, the writer also watching the movie with the same goal and find some image about the topic that we discuss. The sample in this research is the novel "A Room with a view", from the writer understanding by observing the novel, the writers found some topic and one of them was about feminism issues.

4. Discussion

The story was set at a time when women had limited rights and possibilities especially when go to outside, and seldom strayed from conventional, prescribed roles such as faithful wife or mother, but also when individuals were beginning to speak up for more gender equality and women's rights. Gender norms oppress and confine Lucy as a woman, and we witness her progressively achieve independence and establish her flexibility to make herself independent choice throughout the course of the story.

Lucy does not simply stand up to repressive masculine forces, as Forster's story demonstrates. For starters, sexism and gendered stereotypes are not limited to males. Mrs. Honeychurch and Charlotte both have conventional, old-fashioned beliefs about how a woman should act and behave, and they strive to support these values in their own life as well as Lucy's. Mr. Emerson, George, and Mr. Beebe all help Lucy assert her independence. How similar are their efforts to assist Lucy to Cecil's domineering desire to "save" her? When George advises Lucy she should leave Cecil since he just wants to tell her what to do, Lucy brings up this issue. She responds by pointing out that George is doing the same thing by asking her to leave Cecil.

George makes the most extensive remark regarding women and gender issues when he confronts Cecil and tells Lucy how he treats women. When Lucy leaves Cecil later, she echoes George's charges, giving Cecil the impression that someone else is speaking for her. In addition, Mr. Beebe who also supports Lucy who is talented as a pianist to perform abroad and got a vacation rather than staying at home spending time with her rather strict family. In the other words, both of them strongly supported the existence of gender equality during this period, especially in the Honeychurch family. In stark contrast to Cecil, where he loves Lucy not like a woman who wants to be loved spiritually and physically, but he prefers to think of his fiancée as antic display or beautiful painting that is only for collections.

The fact that Lucy dictates and limits many of her encounters as a woman in the story. Even though Lucy asserts her womanhood, she is ultimately communicating with the men (Forster). But that is not to say that Lucy's path toward more independence, or the novel's condemnation of sexist and condescending attitudes in characters like Cecil, aren't important.

5. Conclusion

Feminism issues in this novel explaining about the womanhood and the social class, since the novel set in the country of nobility. The writer conclude that feminism issues and the act of women right was exist in this novel "A Room with a View". Thirty percent of the dialogue contained with masculinity and act of women for express their womanhood.

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